

Impact Response of Protective Metal Foam-Composite Sandwich Plates

Uday K.Vaidya, Selvum Pillay, Chad A.Ulven and Abhay R.S.Gautam
The University of Alabama at Birmingham
Department of Materials Science & Engineering
Birmingham, Alabama, USA

Dana Grow and Biju Mathew
Sioux Manufacturing Co.
Fort Totten, North Dakota, USA

ABSTRACT

Sandwich metal foam-composite structures have the potential to provide significant energy absorption under impact, such as that arising from flying debris, tool drop, projectiles, or crash. When foamed, aluminum provides excellent energy absorption while maintaining high strength. Aluminum foam is rigid, highly porous, and permeable with a constant density. For example, the density of aluminum foams range from 0.5 to 1 g/cm³, with even lower densities possible. Unlike other engineered composites, the foam aluminum is recyclable. The various attractive structural and functional benefits include - high impact damage resistance due to energy absorption, lightweight construction, low thermal conductivity, recycling potential, vibration damping, and the ability to be formed into molds of varying geometry.

In the present work, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) was used to produce aluminum foam/laminated composite sandwich plates. Aluminum foams with two different thicknesses were studied in conjunction with face sheets of S2-glass, E-glass, aramid, and carbon fiber reinforcements laminated using vinyl ester resin. Low velocity impact (LVI) tests up to 5 m/s were conducted to simulate impact conditions. The sandwich construction with S2-glass face sheets in conjunction with aluminum foam was found to yield highest impact resistance under LVI.

KEYWORDS: Metal foam, VARTM, low velocity impact

INTRODUCTION

Cellular foams have exhibited potential use in the naval and marine structures, mass transit, and other transportation applications. Materials with low specific weight and high energy absorbing capacity are of interest for energy management. Highly porous materials with a cellular structure such as closed cell aluminum foams are known to have high specific stiffness combined with a very high specific strength [1,2]. Metal foams are prepared by various processes such as - liquid state processing, solid state processing, electro-deposition technique, and vapor deposition [3,4]. Aluminum foams in particular, show a number of interesting features due to their porous structure. Some characteristics of aluminum foams are - nearly closed porosity, low density, high-energy absorption capacity, reduced thermal and electrical conductivity, good mechanical and acoustic damping, non-flammable, recyclable, and good machinability [1,2,5]. Advantages of foamed metal over polymer foams are their potential for higher operating temperatures, constant properties over time, and absence of noxious fumes during decomposition. Foamed metal is isotropic, cost-effective, and can be recycled if damaged.

Liquid molding techniques are finding increasing use for high-performance applications in a variety of commercial and defense industries [6-8]. This family of processes was originally applied to the pleasure boat industry and was developed as an improvement over wet lay-up of resin on fiberglass. Liquid molding techniques have recently been implemented to produce several types of structural

composites. Sandwich metal foam-composite structures are prone to impact damage from threats such as flying debris, tool drop, projectiles, and/or crash [9, 10]. In the present work, VARTM was used to produce aluminum foam/laminated composite sandwich plates. Aluminum foams with two different thicknesses were studied in conjunction with face sheets of S2-glass, E-glass, aramid, and carbon fiber reinforcements. LVI tests (up to 5 m/s) were conducted to investigate the response of the metal foam sandwich structures to impact threats.

SANDWICH COMPOSITE PROCESSING

Aluminum foam/laminated composite sandwich panels were processed using VARTM. The resin used in the infusion process was Dow 411-11 vinyl ester resin, with 6% Cobalt Napthanate (Conap) catalyst and Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide (MEKP) initiator. The resin was mixed with 0.025% Conap and 1% MEKP as a percentage of resin weight. Prior to infusion, the resin, initiator, and catalyst were added to CAB-O-SIL to form slurry that was applied to the surface of the foam and allowed to dry at 356⁰K for 1 hour. The CAB-O-SIL and resin mixture increased the surface area of the foam to increase adhesion of the facing plies, and also filled in any depressions on the surface. Table 1 lists the sandwich composites processed using two thicknesses (1.59 cm and 2.54 cm) and two densities (10% and 15% aluminum) of 6061-T6-aluminum foam (Supplier: Cymat). Five types of plain woven facing materials were employed, an E-glass fabric (303 g/m²), carbon fabric (363 g/m²), two Kevlar fabrics (468 g/m² and 461 g/m²), and S2-glass fabric (814 g/m²).

Table 1. Sandwich composite designation, foam density, facing material, and foam thickness

Sample	Name	Foam density (%)	Facing material	Foam thickness
1	MF1	15	E-glass	1.59
2	MF2	15	Kevlar 1500	1.59
3	MF3	15	Kevlar 3000	1.59
4	MF4	15	Carbon	1.59
5	MF5	10	E-glass	1.59
6	MF6	10	Kevlar 1500	1.59
7	MF7	10	Kevlar 3000	1.59
8	MF8	10	Carbon	1.59
9	MF9	10	E-glass	2.54
10	MF10	10	Kevlar 1500	2.54
11	MF11	10	Kevlar 3000	2.54
12	MF12	10	Carbon	2.54
13	MF13	15	E-glass	2.54
14	MF14	15	Kevlar 1500	2.54
15	MF15	15	Kevlar 3000	2.54
16	MF16	15	Carbon	2.54
17	MF17	15	S2-glass	1.59
18	MF18	10	S2-glass	1.59
19	MF19	15	S2-glass	2.54
20	MF20	10	S2-glass	2.54

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT TESTS

An instrumented low velocity impact testing equipment was adopted to investigate the damage initiation and propagation in the metal foam composite samples. An Instron 8250-Drop Weight Impact Testing Machine equipped with Dynatup 930I-data acquisition system and a pneumatic clamping fixture was used to conduct the tests. Specimens of dimension 100 mm x 100 mm were clamped along all edges leaving an unexposed circular opening of 76.2 mm. A hemispherical tup with a 19 mm radius was adopted for all tests. Adjusting the drop height controlled the impact velocity. A maximum velocity of 4 m/s was attained in the tests. The force-time-energy histories for all the samples were recorded. The peak force, energy absorbed, total time and load drops in the

force-energy-time plots are indications of damage progression in the sample. For the aluminum foam sandwich composite samples, the initial indentation of the front surface, the damage in the core, and back face damage are identified as characteristic events from the force-energy-time curves.

FORCE-TIME-ENERGY CURVE

A representative force-time-energy curve is provided for a Kevlar face sheet and metal foam core sample of thickness 1.59 cm (Fig. 1). As the indenter makes contact with the specimen, the force-time curve exhibits a linear increase. Upon penetration of the impact side face sheet, a significant load drop is observed. The force-time response, beyond the peak load, indicates the passage/interaction of the tup through the metal foam core. For the samples where the tup penetrated the core, and made contact with the bottom face sheet, a secondary peak is observed denoting the load carried by the bottom face sheet. For sample with bottom side penetration, a secondary load drop is observed. As seen, energy absorption is maximized through this construction because penetration has to occur through the three components (top face sheet, the core, and the bottom face sheet), which then constitutes sandwich material failure. The energy-to-peak load, and the total energy absorbed are recorded. These are indicative of impact causing fracture of top face, and the total energy absorbed by the sample.

LVI RESPONSE OF CARBON, KEVLAR, E-GLASS AND S2-GLASS FACE SHEET

Figures 2 and 3 provide a comprehensive idea of the results obtained for different class of sandwich specimens. The general mechanism of energy absorbed for the sandwich samples was as follows: a) the top face sheet in all cases (i.e., E-glass, carbon, and Kevlar fiber) the failure occurred by localized shear fracture of the face sheet material (Figure 2). The difference in failure was observed in the S2-glass fiber (where the strain-to-failure of S2-glass fiber is about 4%, and the weave is coarser) face sheet material in contact with the tup. For the sandwich plate with S2-glass fabric face sheet, the top face did not completely fail, but resulted in straining of the fibers (indicated by whitening of the damaged area) and compression crushing in the thickness direction. The damage was highly localized for the carbon, Kevlar and E-glass on the top face sheet, while it spread across the face sheet for the S2-glass face sheet. The latter did not exhibit penetration, b) the metal foam core failed by pulverizing of the metal particles, when the top face sheet failed. The pulverization of the core is unique to the continuous particulate foam chosen in our present work.

Figure 1. Typical LVI force-time-energy curve

Figure 2. LVI impact failure of aluminum metal foam core with a, b) E-glass face sheet, c, d) Kevlar face sheet, e, f) carbon face sheet. Note figures a, c, e are impact side top view, and figure b, d, f are cross-sections at impact location.

For the S2-glass samples, the top face exerted a compressive force to the core, and the core underwent progressive compression crushing, as shown in Fig. 3, c) the bottom face sheet had an extended damage, due to flexure and tensile side stresses. In some samples the back face damage extended to the supports.

From observations of the LVI results, it was interpreted that for maximizing energy absorption, the fracture/failure of the top face sheet must be delayed. The use of a coarser weave high strain S2-glass fiber exhibited superior performance. The broader the damage to the top face sheet, the better is the utilization of core performance. This is illustrated in the comparison of the failure modes through the core in Fig. 3 (for S2-glass/aluminum foam) and Fig. 2 (for E-glass, Kevlar, and carbon / aluminum foam). For the S2-glass face sheet, the foam is progressively crushed as a larger area of the face sheet

compresses it, enhancing energy absorption mechanisms; while for the E-glass, Kevlar, and carbon the localized top face sheet failure results in core pulverization, and lesser energy absorption. Conversely, when damage localization is desirable, the latter arrangements may be better suited.

Figure 3. LVI failure of aluminum metal foam with S2-glass face sheet. a) impact side top view, b) cross-section at impact location

INFLUENCE OF CORE THICKNESS AND CORE DENSITY

Figures 4 and 5 summarize the peak force values of metal foam sandwich plates with Kevlar 1500, Kevlar 3000, E-glass, carbon, and S2-glass face sheets. The impact velocity is 4.5 m/s for all the tests considered. Although peak forces only are shown in the figures, the trends obtained are consistent with the absorbed energies for the samples. Several observations made are as follows: a) The E-glass face sheet samples showed the lowest impact performance. This is attributed to the low compression/tension characteristics of E-glass fiber, b) the carbon fiber shows the second lowest performance amongst the fibers. The brittle failure characteristic of carbon under compression is attributed to the poor impact response. However, the carbon samples exhibit highest modulus in the linear portion up to peak load, typical of high modulus carbon. The tensile side (back side of the impact) of most carbon samples did not exhibit failure due to high tensile load bearing capacity of carbon fiber, c) the Kevlar 1500 and Kevlar 3000 show superior and comparable response. Interestingly, the Kevlar 1500 shows superior performance for thicker (2.54 cm) core, while Kevlar 3000 is superior for the 1.59 cm core. It appears that strain rate characteristics of the different Kevlar grades influence the impact response. The thicker (2.54 cm) core is more rigid in transverse impact than the thinner (1.59 cm) core, which may promote shearing for the less flexible Kevlar 3000 fiber. As a result, similar to carbon, the Kevlar 3000 has higher initial modulus, but shears with less flexibility, d) the S2-glass fiber shows the highest performance for all conditions considered. The high strain rate and coarser weave are attributed to higher performance of the S2-glass.

Peak load increases with increase in core thickness for all samples tested. This is due to the rigidity of the sample and resistance to penetration. The influence of core density (10% or 15% aluminum) was not significant. The 15% aluminum density core was slightly higher in performance with respect to peak loads. The energy absorption is maximized with lower core density, as energy dissipation mechanisms are obtained from core crushing behavior.

a)

b)

Figure 4. Comparison of LVI performance for sandwich plates with different face sheets impacted at impact velocity of 4.5 m/s. The metal foam core thickness is 1.59 cm. a) 10% foam density, b) 15% foam density.

a)

b)

Figure 5. Comparison of LVI performance for sandwich plates with different face sheets impacted at impact velocity of 4.5 m/s. The metal foam core thickness is 2.54 cm. a) 10% foam density, b) 5% foam density

CONCLUSIONS

- CVARTM was an effective technique to produce a hybrid material consisting of aluminum foam and composite plies.
- The impact resistance was most importantly a function of the areal density, coarseness of the weave and strength of the plies constituting the strike face.
- For the impact tests, S-2 glass fabric was not penetrated and laminate failed by crushing of the foam. In some cases the foam broke into small fragments. A coarser weave of S2-glass fabric as the top face sheet enabled maximization of energy spread to the aluminum foam core, and thereby its greater utilization.
- E-glass and carbon fabric did not provide effective resistance.

- Kevlar facing plies were penetrated on the strike face but not on the back face. Penetration could be eliminated by adding more plies to the front, or by utilizing a coarser weave to get similar damage mechanisms as were obtained with the S2-glass face sheet.

REFERENCES

1. H.D. Kunze, J. Baumeister, J. Banhart, J. and M. Weber, M. "P/M Technology for the Production of Metal Foams", *Powder metallurgy International*, 25, 182-185 (1993).
2. L.J. Gibson and M.F. Ashby, *Cellular Solids –Structure and Properties*, 2nd edition, 357-358 (1997).
3. J. Banhart, "Manufacture, Characterization and Application of Cellular Metals and Metal Foams", *Progress in Material Science*, 46, 559-632 (2001).
4. G.J. Davies and S. Zhen, "Metallic Foams: Their Production, Properties and Applications", *J. Mat. Sci.* 18, 1899-1911 (1983).
5. J. Baumeister, J. Banhart, and M. Weber, "Aluminum Foams for Transport Industry", *Materials & Design*, 18, 217-220 (1997).
6. W. Michaeli and J. Topker, "RTM for Railway Applications: Development of a Tram Front End Bumper", *SAMPE J.* 37, 69-74 (2001).
7. T. Pike, et al., "Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding of a Layered Structural Laminate for Application on Ground Combat Vehicles", *Proc. 28th Int SAMPE Tech. Conf*, Seattle, WA, 374-380 (1996).
8. E.J. Rigas, et al., "Affordable Thick Composite Processing for Army Applications", *Proc. 14th Tech. Conf. of the Am. Soc. for Composites*, 14, 242-251 (1999).
9. E. Herup, *Low Velocity Impact on Composite Sandwich Plates*. Ph.D. Dissertation, Air Force Institute of Technology, AFIT/DS/ENY/96-11, Dayton OH, July (1996).
10. C.L. Wu and C.T. Sun, "Low Velocity Impact Damage in Composite Sandwich Beams", *Composite Structures*, 24, 21-27 (1996).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Support provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF) SBIR Phase I Award No. DMI-0128164 to Sioux Manufacturing is gratefully acknowledged.